

Effect of nucleophile on the kinetics of the reactions of *O*-(2',4'-dinitrophenyl)-4-phenyl-3-buten-2-one oxime in acetonitrile

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The kinetics of the reactions of *O*-(2',4'-dinitrophenyl)-4-phenyl-3-buten-2-one oxime have been studied with piperidine, cyclohexylamine, *n*-butylamine and pyrrolidine in acetonitrile at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Base catalysis has been observed with piperidine and pyrrolidine. Mechanistic interpretation is given.

Many workers studying aromatic nucleophilic substitution reactions have used amines as nucleophiles or as leaving groups. It has been shown that base catalysis occurs with nucleophiles of high basicity^{1,2}. Nucleophilicity towards aromatic carbon is roughly related to the basicity of the attacking nucleophile, but the catalytic effect does not always depend on the basicity of the amine³ and hence fails to give a linear Bronsted plot in many cases. Bernasconi and Rossi² observed that secondary amines are usually more prone⁴ to base catalysis than analogous reactions with primary amines. In order to have more information on aminolysis reactions, we have studied the reactions of *O*-(2',4'-dinitrophenyl)-4-phenyl-3-buten-2-one oxime (**I**) with different amines in acetonitrile.

Results and discussion

The reactions of *O*-(2',4'-dinitrophenyl)-4-phenyl-3-buten-2-one oxime (**I**) with piperidine, cyclohexylamine, *n*-butylamine and pyrrolidine were followed at the λ_{\max} of the corresponding principal product *N*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl) amine. All the reactions followed overall second order kinetics, first order with respect to each reactant. The observed rate constants are listed in Table 1.

The pseudo first order rate constants (k_0) increased with increase in base concentration. In acetonitrile the reactions of **I** with *n*-butylamine and cyclohexylamine are not base

Table 1. Rate constants for the reactions of **I** with different nucleophiles in acetonitrile at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Nucleophile	[Nu]	k_0	k_A	
	$10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	10^{-4} s^{-1}	$10^{-4} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ dm}^{-3}$	
Cyclohexylamine	4.5	1.12	24.9	
	10.0	2.49	24.9	
	20.0	5.02	25.1	
	30.0	7.59	25.3	
	5.0	2.50	50.0	
Piperidine	5.5	3.11	56.5	
	6.0	3.61	60.2	
	6.5	4.26	65.5	
	7.0	4.50	64.3	
	7.5	5.34	71.2	
	2.0	3.63	181.5	
	3.0	5.46	182.0	
<i>n</i> -Butylamine	5.0	9.60	192.0	
	6.0	11.69	194.8	
	7.0	3.81	197.3	
	Pyrrolidine	1.0	5.95	595.0
		1.5	10.66	710.7
		2.0	13.59	679.5
		2.5	18.61	744.4
3.0		22.80	760.0	
3.5		29.32	837.7	

catalyzed. Those with piperidine and pyrrolidine have a linear dependence on the nucleophile concentration.

When the condition $k_{-1} \ll k_2 + k_3[B]$ does not hold in equation (1), the reaction is base catalyzed,

$$k_A = \frac{k_1(k_2 + k_3[B])}{k_1 + k_2 + k_3[B]} \quad (1)$$

and if $k_{-1} \gg k_2 + k_3 [B]$ then there is a linear dependence of k_A on $[B]$ and equation (1) has the form given in equation (2),

$$k_A = k' + k''[B] \quad (2)$$

where $k' = k_1 k_2 / k_{-1}$ the intercept is the non-catalytic and $k'' (= k_1 k_3 / k_{-1})$, the slope) the catalytic rate constants.

The equation (1) is interpreted in the light of Bunnett and Randall⁵ (Scheme 1).

The plots of k_A versus $[base]$ were linear in all cases. The experimental results can be explained by equation (2). From an analysis of kinetic data for the reactions of (1) with amines in acetonitrile, attack of amine (in the case of piperidine and pyrrolidine) at the nitroactivated carbon forming a zwitterionic intermediate (T^\pm) and its slow decomposition is indicated (Scheme 2). However in the case of *n*-butylamine and cyclohexylamine rate determining formation of the zwitterionic intermediate is envisaged (Scheme 3).

For the reactions of (1) with piperidine and pyrrolidine characteristic slope and intercept were obtained (Table 2).

The value of k''/k' is moderate (>50) in the case of piperidine. This reaction is, therefore, base catalyzed and the decomposition of the intermediate is rate limiting. For the reactions of (1) with pyrrolidine, the k''/k' value is 19.95. According to Bunnett's principle this low value does not represent true base catalysis.

The reactions were also carried out at various tempera-

Table 2. The catalytic (k'') and non-catalytic (k') rate constants for the reaction of I with piperidine and pyrrolidine in acetonitrile

Nucleophile	$k'/10^{-3}$ $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1} \text{dm}^3$	$k''/10^{-2}$ $\text{mol}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{dm}^6$	k''/k' $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{dm}^3$
Piperidine	1.0	8.4	84.0
Pyrrolidine	47.0	93.75	19.95

tures and the rate constants increased with increase in temperature. The relevant data are shown in Table 3.

All the reactions followed Arrhenius relationship. The activation parameters for the reactions were calculated and are compiled in Table 4. The values of entropy of activation are high and negative indicating crowded nature of the transition state in each case.

It can be seen that negative values of entropy of

Table 3. Effect of temperature on the rate of the reactions of *O*-(2',4'-dinitrophenyl)-4-phenyl-3-buten-2-one oxime (**I**) with different nucleophiles in acetonitrile

Nucleophile	[Nu]/10 ⁻² mol dm ⁻³	Temp. °C	k ₀ /10 ⁻⁴ s ⁻¹
Piperidine	5.0	20	2.79
		25	2.84
		30	2.92
		35	2.50
		40	3.08
Cyclohexylamine	40.0	20	5.19
		25	7.71
		30	8.45
		35	10.46
		40	14.85
<i>n</i> -Butylamine	3.0	20	3.21
		25	4.41
		30	5.17
		35	5.46
		40	6.72
Pyrrolidine	1.0	20	3.97
		25	4.11
		30	4.24
		35	5.95
		40	4.51

Table 4. Activation parameters for the reactions of **I** with different nucleophiles

Nucleophile	E _a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG [#] kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS [#] J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Piperidine	4.40	90.05 (±4.5)	281.9 (±1.4)
Cyclohexylamine	38.29	91.40 (±2.9)	177.9 (±1.1)
<i>n</i> -Butylamine	24.89	86.7 (±3.1)	205.7 (±1.2)
Pyrrolidine	4.98	84.8 (±5.1)	263.5 (±1.9)

activation are high for catalyzed reactions than those of the non-catalyzed ones. The high negative value supports formation of products through ordered eight membered hydrogen bonded cyclic transition state.

Experimental

Cyclohexylamine, piperidine, *n*-butylamine, pyrrolidine and acetonitrile (G.R., Merck) were purified⁶. Benzalacetone was converted to its oxime as per literature

procedure⁷ and characterized. An equimolar mixture of oxime of benzalacetone and 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene in methanol was treated with sodium methoxide, warmed and stirred for few minutes to obtain light yellow crystals of *O*-(2',4'-dinitrophenyl)-4-phenyl-3-buten-2-one oxime. Recrystallization from ethanol yielded **I**, m.p. 163–165°; ν_{max} (KBr) 1344, 1529 (C=N) cm⁻¹; λ_{max} (acetonitrile) 303.4 nm (log ε = 4.41).

Kinetic procedure :

The kinetics of the reactions was followed spectrophotometrically using a Shimadzu UV 2100, UV/VIS spectrophotometer fitted with temperature controller. Rate constants were measured under pseudo first order conditions following the rate expression,

$$\log \left[\frac{A_{\infty} - A_0}{A_{\infty} - A_t} \right] = k_0 t \quad (3)$$

where, A_∞, A_t and A₀ are the absorbances at infinity, at time *t* and zero respectively. The entire rate calculations were carried out on a DEC. 2050 computer. The programmer was set to calculate average rate constant, fitted rate constant, correlation coefficient; root mean square error, percentage error and standard deviation in the rate constant. Random errors, if any, were deleted. Kinetic runs having correlation coefficient less than 0.993 were discarded. The products were identified by comparing m.p., R_f values, IR and UV/VIS data with those of the authentic samples. In all cases *N*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)amine and 4-phenyl-3-buten-2-one oxime were obtained in quantitative yield.

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